

ACUTE RESPIRATORY FAILURE DURING LABOUR IN A PATIENT WITH CONGENITAL MITRAL VALVE REGURGITATION

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Abstract

Pregnancy, delivery and postpartum hide risks of cardio-pulmonary complications in women with cardiac diseases. Anesthesia, analgesia and correct treatment can reduce significantly maternal and fetal mortality. Epidural analgesia during labour decreases pain-induced production of catecholamines, risk of thromboembolism, and provides stable hemodynamic. Each uterine contraction increases cardiac output with 30 %.

Raised preload could worsen pulmonary hypertension, which already existed in pregnant women with congestive heart failure and pulmonary edema may occur. That may cause acute fetal respiratory failure and emergency caesarean section must be done. In these cases general anesthesia with rapid sequence induction is preferred. However there are not enough studies for strategies of mechanical ventilation during surgery and postpartum.

Keywords: NYHA, BIPAP, PaO₂, PEEP.

Introduction: Incidence of cardiac diseases in pregnant women varies from 0,3 to 3,5%. Valvular heart diseases could be categorized as congenital, acquired, corrected and uncorrected, cyanotic and non-cyanotic. Asymptomatic patients during second and third trimester of pregnancy may develop symptoms like progressive dyspnea, orthopnea, paroxysmal nocturnal dyspnea, oedema, swollen neck veins, hepatojugular reflux, diastolic murmur, arrhythmia. According to the criteria for heart failure during pregnancy, systolic blood pressure must be higher than 160 mmHg or lower than 90 mmHg diastolic blood pressure must be higher than 100 mmHg or lower than 50 mmHg, heart rate faster than 120 / min, respiratory rate over 30 / min or under 10 / min. Saturation lower than 95 % on room air, diuresis under 35 ml / h (1,3,17). During pregnancy typical physiological changes occur: cardiac output increases mainly because of enlarged with 50 % volume of plasma. Volume of erythrocytes increases with 20-30%, that causes dilutional anemia. Heart rate is accelerated (5,19). Minute ventilation is also increased as consequence of higher tidal volume and respiratory rate. (physiological hyperventilation).

Because of the higher position of diaphragm functional residual capacity is decreased, and hypoxia may appear rapidly after induction of general anesthesia.

Pulmonary compliance is also reduced. Respiratory alkalosis is common, oxygen consumption is increased. (7,16,20). In pregnant women is recommended partial arterial pressure of oxygen to be higher than 75 mmHg. (PaO₂), that protects from fetal hypoxia. Incidence of cardiac and respiratory complications is higher during pregnancy, delivery and postpartum in patients categorized as NYHA III-IV, in those with pulmonary hypertension, uncorrected cyanotic heart diseases, severe aortic and mitral stenosis (18). During delivery intense pain causes production of large amount of catecholamine, which increases heart rate and myocardial contractility. During each uterine contraction cardiac output increases with 20-30% and preload, end-diastolic left ventricular volume are also extended.

(4,13). That could lead to pulmonary hypertension and edema in pregnant women with valvular heart diseases. During labour and in early postpartum pulmonary capillary pressure rises with 10 mm Hg. That may cause pulmonary edema in patients with severe heart failure. After delivery of fetus, the aortocaval compression is released and that increases cardiac output. Epidural analgesia is recommended in those patients during labour, because it reduces level of catecholamines also preload, heart rate, afterload and risk of thromboembolism (2). In cases of Cesarean section epidural anesthesia is considered safe for pregnant women with valvular heart diseases. It doesn't cause hemodynamic instability. Effect of epidural anesthesia is slow and prolonged, so in cases of emergency general anesthesia is preferred. That may provide secure airway, hemodynamic stability, analgesia, monitoring of respiratory and hemodynamic parameters (8).

Case report: It concerns pregnant woman at term, who was admitted in University Hospital „Manchin Dom” in Sofia, Bulgaria. She was multipara almost in the second stage of labour and epidural analgesia was not applied. The patient had twelve pregnancies and congenital mitral regurgitation. During her admission in the hospital she complained from dyspnea, cough with white sputum, fatigue from one week. These symptoms have worsened on the day of her admission. The pregnant woman was defined as NYHA III. When the woman was admitted to the hospital she was not febrile, her skin and visible mucous membranes were pales, she was conscious, with bilateral vesicular breathing, wheezing saturation 93 % on air, respiratory rate 25-30 / min, arterial blood pressure 140/90 mm Hg, heart rate 70-80/ min.

Her laboratory results were normal, except CRP, which was 147. During period of expulsion of the fetus the patient developed acute respiratory failure- she turned cyanotic with tachypnea dyspnea, and bradypnea occurred later. The patient was with stable arterial blood pressure and sinus tachycardia- heart rate 140/

min, saturation 70 % on air. She was treated with oxygen mask with reservoir bag. Arterial blood gases (ABG) analysis was taken and it showed respiratory and metabolic acidosis - pH -7,1, PaO_2 -96 mm Hg, PaCO_2 -48 mm Hg, HCO_3 -11, $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ -195 mm Hg. Acute fetal asphyxia happened and it was decided that she had to undergo emergent Cesarean section. General anesthesia with rapid sequence induction was performed. As intravenous anesthetic was used thiopental-5 mg / kg, and as neuromuscular relaxant was used succinylcholine- 1mg / kg. The patient was with stable hemodynamic during induction in general anesthesia. For maintenance of it inhalation anesthetic sevoflurane was applied in minimal concentration and non- depolarizing neuromuscular relaxant atracurium was used. Analgesia was performed with fentanyl after delivery of baby, tramadol, ketoprofen, paracetamol. As uterotonic was used oxytocin. Bolus doses of oxytocin are not recommended in patients with heart diseases, because they could reduce rapidly arterial blood pressure. In cases of mitral regurgitation bradycardia could increase pulmonary arterial pressure. Therefore in cases of hypotension ephedrine was preferred vasopressor. Magnesium treatment could cause hypotension and bradycardia.

General anesthesia provides secure airways, and decreases minute ventilation, work of breathing, oxygen consumption, preload. Patient was ventilated with volume controlled mechanical ventilation -tidal volume 6ml / kg, FiO_2 – 80 %, respiratory rate 12 /мин, PEEP- 8 mBr, Saturation was 89-90 %. Monitoring of hemodynamic consisted invasive measurement of arterial blood pressure, central venous line, which was used for estimation of central venous pressure. ABG analysis showed hypoxia, respiratory alkalosis- pH -7,46, PaCO_2 - 29,5 mm Hg, PaO_2 -62 mm Hg, HCO_3 -23.

Cesarean section proceeded without complications. As the patient was with severe mitral regurgitation we had to avoid hypertension, bradycardia, arrhythmia and raise of cardiac output. Hypoxia, acidosis, hypercapnea, hyperventilation could increase pulmonary arterial pressure. After operation patient was admitted to intensive care unit, where she was ventilated by Bilevel positive airway pressure (BIPAP) with following parameters - FiO_2 -50 %, Pinsp .-20 mBr, PEEP-10 mBr, respiratory rate-12/ min, Saturation 93-94 %. ABG analysis that was taken one hour after BIPAP ventilation was started showed improvement- pH -7,42, PaO_2 -126 mm Hg, PaCO_2 -32 mmHg, HCO_3 - 23, $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ - 252. Hemodynamic was stable, continuous infusions of fentanyl and midazolam was started. Chest X-Ray was performed and it showed bilateral pleural effusions and perichilar haze, enlargement of cardiac silhouette, Kerley B lines (horizontal lines in the periphery of the lower posterior lungs field), upper lobe pulmonary venous congestion and interstitial edema.

Echocardiography was made and revealed depressed systolic function, ejection fraction was estimated-38%, severe mitral and tricuspid regurgitation. As diagnosis was considered acute pulmonary edema caused by physiological changes during labour in patient with severe mitral regurgitation. The patient was treated with diuretic therapy (furosemide), as vasodilator nitroglycerin was used on continuous intravenous

infusion. We added also antibiotic and anticoagulant therapy.

On the next her condition was improved, her hemodynamic was stable without sinus tachycardia, arterial blood gases analysis was also improved. The process of weaning was started. The patient was ventilated by mode of pressure support mechanical ventilation – (PSV), Pinsp . -10 mBr, PEEP- 6 mBr, FiO_2 -40 %. ABG analysis- pH -7,44, PaO_2 -177 mm Hg, PaCO_2 -30 mm Hg, HCO_3 - 23, $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ - 440. On the same day she was extubated successfully. Her length of hospital stay was 5 days. She was discharged and later consulted in cardiac surgery department.

Discussion: Physiological changes during pregnancy and labour could cause cardio- pulmonary complications especially at pregnant women defined as NYHA III-IV. Pain during uterine contraction in first stage of labour and perineal pain in second stage when expulsion of fetus happens leads to release of large amount of catecholamines. That causes tachycardia, hypertension, increased myocardial contractility and oxygen consumption. Each uterine contraction adds blood volume to systemic blood circulation. That leads to raised preload and cardiac output. In patients with heart valvular diseases these changes might cause pulmonary hypertension. In parturients with congestive heart failure acute pulmonary edema, acute respiratory failure and acute intrapartum fetal asphyxia could occur. Epidural analgesia reduces amount of released catecholamines, provides stable hemodynamic in process of delivery. It also decreases preload and prevents from thromboembolism. Epidural catheter could also be used when cesarean section is needed. Spinal anesthesia decreases rapidly arterial blood pressure and preload. So treatment with crystalloid and colloid infusion as well as vasopressors might be applied.(15) Epidural anesthesia has similar, but slower effect on patient's hemodynamic. So anesthesiologist has enough time to correct it with vasopressors and colloid and crystalloid infusions. General anesthesia might be applied in cases of acute respiratory failure, heart failure, treatment with anticoagulants, thrombocytopenia, eclampsia, e.t Endotracheal intubation is the most safe method for airway's protection. During induction in general anesthesia hypertension and tachycardia could occur. That could be avoided with administration of beta blockers with short duration of action, or with opiates like remifentanyl. The most suitable for induction in general anesthesia is etomidate, because it provides stable hemodynamic. Pregnant women with congestive heart failure are exposed to risk of paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia, ventricular tachycardia and ventricular fibrillation. (14). Previous studies proved higher maternal mortality in pregnant patients with severe mitral stenosis who underwent general anesthesia in compared to those who were operated with epidural anesthesia (2). Inhalation anesthetics suppress myocardial contractility, volume controlled mechanical ventilation increases pulmonary vascular resistance, that could lead to pulmonary edema in patients with pre-existing pulmonary arterial hypertension. While titrated epidural anesthesia decreases systemic vascular resistance, preload and cardiac output.(18). In parturients defined as NYHA III-IV is recommended monitoring of invasive arterial

blood pressure, central venous pressure, echocardiography, and in cases with pulmonary hypertension is useful pulmonary catheter for measuring pulmonary capillary pressure. After delivery of fetus cardiac output increases, because of decompression of abdominal aorta and vena cava inferior, that could also worsen pulmonary hypertension. In this case of peripartur acute respiratory failure diagnosis as amniotic embolism, pulmonary thromboembolism, peripartur cardiomyopathy, pneumonia, sepsis, preeclampsia could also be considered (4). Fetal hypoxia could happen when maternal saturation is under 95 % and partial arterial oxygen pressure (PaO₂) is under 70 mm Hg (10). According to previous researches non-invasive mechanical ventilation could be used successfully in pregnant women with pulmonary edema, pneumonia, severe anemia, bronchial asthma, e.t. The most common used mode is BIPAP with parameters- P_{insp}. 12-25 mBr, PEEP- 5-10 mBr. (22) Some of advantages of non-invasive mechanical ventilation are no need of neuromuscular relaxation, lower doses of sedative drugs, lower risk of nosocomial pneumonia, e.t. Pregnant women are considered to have full stomach, and there is huge risk of pulmonary aspiration syndrome during induction in general anesthesia. In all cases of respiratory acidosis, signs of respiratory muscles fatigue, lost of consciousness, endotracheal intubation and mechanical ventilation are inevitables. Because thoracic compliance is reduced in pregnant patients, they could tolerate higher values of plateau pressure (P_{plat})- until 30 mBr (17). In pregnant women intraabdominal pressure is increased and application of prone position is difficult. (6). Many drugs that are used for sedation could pass through uteroplacental barrier and cumulates in fetus. Propofol causes muscular hypotension and depresses neuromuscular activity of fetus. There are not enough studies about respiratory parameters in pregnant women, but low tidal volume 4-6 ml/ kg and P_{plat} under 30 mBr are recommended. The value of applied PEEP might prevent from hypoxia.

Conclusion: Cardiac diseases are one of the main causes of maternal and fetal mortality. Management of the patients is multidisciplinary. Anesthesiologist has to provide suitable anesthesia, analgesia monitoring of respiratory and hemodynamic parameters and treatment in intensive care unit.

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